

(CASE REPORT)

When fungi collide: An uncommon presentation of *Candida lusitaniae* in a tuberculous patient

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Abstract

Introduction: *Candida lusitaniae* is a rare opportunistic yeast, often resistant to amphotericin B, and involved in a small percentage of genitourinary infections. It mainly affects immunocompromised patients.

Case Report: We report the case of a 67-year-old diabetic man admitted for acute abdominal pain. Biological and radiological investigations revealed a pulmonary infection associated with tuberculosis confirmed by PCR (*Mycobacterium tuberculosis*) and a fungal infection (*Cryptococcus laurentii*). Ten days after ICU admission, a urine culture revealed the presence of *Candida lusitaniae*, effectively treated with fluconazole.

Conclusion: This case illustrates the complexity of opportunistic infections in vulnerable patients and highlights the importance of rapid, accurate, and comprehensive biological diagnostics to guide targeted therapy.

Keywords: *Candida lusitaniae*; Fluconazole; Amphotericin B; Tuberculosis; Immunosuppression

1. Introduction

Candida species are responsible for a wide range of fungal infections, with *Candida albicans* being the most commonly encountered. *Candida lusitaniae*, a non-*albicans* species, is less common but deserves special attention due to its intrinsic resistance to amphotericin B and its preference for immunocompromised hosts. Its detection relies on rigorous mycological diagnosis and contextual clinical interpretation.

2. Case Report

We report the case of a 67-year-old male patient, known to have diabetes for 6 months (exact duration to be specified), on oral antidiabetics, admitted for diffuse abdominal pain with vomiting and cessation of stools and gas for 10 days, all in a context of general health deterioration.

Upon admission, the patient was conscious, afebrile, tachycardic, and hypertensive, with generalized abdominal tenderness and bilateral crackles on pulmonary examination. ECG showed no repolarization or conduction disturbances, and transthoracic echocardiography revealed good biventricular function with minimal aortic insufficiency. COVID-19 antigen testing was negative. Laboratory tests showed elevated CRP, PCT, and D-dimers, along with hypokalemia, hyponatremia, and liver function abnormalities (elevated conjugated bilirubin, LDH, and alkaline phosphatase).

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A thoraco-abdominopelvic CT scan revealed infectious bronchopneumopathy with sac-like bronchial dilation and secondary infection, associated with bilateral simple renal polycystosis and functional rectocolic fecal stasis without signs of bowel obstruction. Bronchial aspiration and cytobacteriological analysis identified *Cryptococcus laurentii* and *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (rifampicin-sensitive, confirmed by PCR). Aspergillus serology was negative.

The patient was stabilized and started on anti-tuberculosis therapy (Rifampicin 150 mg, Isoniazid 75 mg, Pyrazinamide 400 mg, and Ethambutol 275 mg). However, on the tenth day of ICU stay, urine culture (cytobacteriological exam) revealed *Candida lusitanae*, which was fluconazole-sensitive according to antifungal susceptibility testing and was treated accordingly.

3. Discussion

This case highlights the critical role of medical biology in diagnosing rare fungal infections such as *Candida lusitanae*, an uncommon opportunistic yeast frequently resistant to amphotericin B and primarily found in immunocompromised patients [1,2]. In this diabetic patient admitted to the ICU, candiduria due to *C. lusitanae* was diagnosed through urine cytobacteriological examination, followed by antifungal susceptibility testing which guided effective fluconazole treatment. The presence of concurrent pulmonary infections with *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* and *Cryptococcus laurentii* reflects the underlying immunosuppression and the necessity for broad microbiological screening [3]. This case emphasizes the need for a comprehensive, rapid, and multidisciplinary diagnostic approach, involving both clinicians and laboratory professionals, to ensure optimal and targeted management of emerging hospital-acquired fungal infections.

4. Conclusion

This case illustrates the complexity of opportunistic infections in fragile patients and highlights the crucial importance of medical biology for rapid and accurate diagnosis. Isolation, identification, and sensitivity testing of pathogens allow for effective multidisciplinary care, ultimately improving patient outcomes.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

Statement of ethical approval

The study was conducted in accordance with ethical standards. Approval was obtained from the appropriate ethics committee.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

References

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